

IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON SOCIETY

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Abstract

Social Media is no more a new phenomenon and the discussion on its role and impact of society is no more a new subject. However on accounts of increase in number of IT devices used for this media and the increase in number of programming on internet after fore bookand twitter and the whatsapp and IMO new questions have arisen while third world states have been found expressing their reservations. On the other hand intellectuals and civic society organization have started blaming that international agencies are using this media to prepare data to be used for curbing human rights and particularly the right of expression. However the positive role of the social media and its positive impact on society is so much significant that it could not be minimized or negated. The role of social media for interconnectivity level and as a source of information and knowledge for researches and for the academia is so immensely significant praising it. But the negative aspects particularly in the use of devices of social media and the negative impacts on the society however need a constant check by the authorities of the network programming research is direly needed to monitor the impacts of social media both positive and negative so that the society could benefit more. Use of social media is increasing day by day all over the countries on the globe and so it is the contribution of social media (after the invention of the devices) that the world is turning into a global village. It should be noted that the electronic devices created for intercommunication the PC, smart phone, tablet etc, not only created inter connectivity with respect to communication of information but the internet programming like face book, Whatsapp, IMO, Twitter helped the people to communicate their ideas and the comments on every type of social events and the happenings. This created the phenomenon of social media which help turn the world into a global village. The use of social media is on rapid increase particularly in third world countries like Pakistan and its neighbouring state. The use of social media can be observed and analyzed through the information regarding number of users of social media and the devices. However social media is now haunting the ruling government and the establishment of third world countries with reference to their political reservations. In our country social media has become a target of criticism for its independence and “the extra use of freedom of expression, governments are trying to clamp it down but it seems a futile exercise as government could control its down citizen only while social media is now a global activity.

PURPOSE OF STUDY

Social media, a phenomenon emerged with the beginning of 21st Century has benefited the society with reference to creating and promoting awareness among general people regarding social and political issues and help the academia immensely. The growth of social media users and the sale of social media devices (IT devices) said to be 5.7 percent exhibit its impact people of every walk of life have welcome social media which means it has positive notions of impacts. Study has been made to confirm the impact theoretically the traditional tabular data has not been used and results are deducted logically using authenticated information

Introduction

Social media is under frequent use in our society and effecting our society both in positive and negative aspects. However, in present situation positive effects are more visible and dominated use of social media is mostly based on smart phones, tablets and laptops. Smart phones are used to get connected with people through messages and direct conversation. They are also the to provide information including news main source documentaries and particularly to express views in the shape of comments on both political and social issues. Social media devices used by individuals has created quick connectivity and reactivity among people of the age. Youth of the society are using the devices for their personal use including amusement.

Social media is not a new phenomenon now. It has been known as used both on local and international level. On one hand have it is a source of information on international level it provides news items and other information of the globe to the general public including both the resource persons and others from all walks of life while on the other hands it helps communication among people of the world and provide them to express themselves that is expressing their personal views regarding all that which is happening and all that which comes under discussion of and on.

The quick connectivity among people has now availed its new and real meaning. Priorly the connectivity had limited meaning as the social media was confined to TV and films and the ideas on various issues both reality and fiction which could create awareness among the people on nearly equal level with a difference that the intellectual level of the individuals caused the difference. Yet it is a fact that prior to the creation and use of the modern electronic devices of information technology including personal computers and after words the devices like tablets and particularly the smart phone and their use, the term social media was something vague an

unconceived. In fact the creation and use of devices that is latest IT devices has provided the facility of expression the views for the individuals of the society. On the other hand the frequent transfer of individuals views and views of individuals among each other through the programming on internet used by the smart phones and the PCs has created the real meaning to the concept of social media.

It is also important to note that after quick connectivity among the people through social media devices the reactivity on the messages and regarding the contents of the messages which appear through Facebook and the twitter has contributed a lot to the term social enriching its meaning.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Plethora of studies has been conducted on this topic.

The social media is no more a new phenomenon now and also the impact of the social media on the society is no more a new subject of discussion.

The writers of the articles and the researchers have expressed mixed views of satisfaction on promotion of social media and on the other hand expressed concerned on uncontrolled negative impact and use of devices. Majority has confined their views on use of devices and its commercial impact. Social impact has not been highlighted properly. The articles include (1) use of social media in promotion of film industry and particularly creating atmosphere of eagerness among audience and general public to welcome new moves created by world producers of film so that earning by displaying the movies on screen may cross the limited of revenue. (2) Impact on general public. (3) Sale of devices on social media and (4) Use of devices for entertainment and also for academic use by small section of population.

Public to get latest situation of current affairs and latest news for students use of internet websites and the programmes like Facebook and Google provide a ready source of information used for academic purpose. For research scholars all types of data is available on websites which are easily available and accessibly through commonly used devices.

Most significant use of social media and its impact is that it is a source of awareness and connectivity with the issues both social and political for people of every age limit. Also it is a source of expressing views. This all is helpful in creating harmony among people which will ultimately create unity among people of every area and section of country and population.

The negative role of government that is its efforts to control the social media in order to stop expression of political views by the people and particularly to stop anti government views on facebook and twitter, is very much harmful for positive impact of social media on society. There is a dire need to research the situation and suggest remedies in this regard.

ANALYSIS

1) POSITIVE ASPECT:

The positive role of social media require discussion on its benefit earned by researchers, scholars, students and also those who teach them, with reference to gaining knowledge through resources provided by social media particularly the website providing research articles and research papers. Even entire text of important books on majority of subjects are available through social media.

Social media is a great source of imparting knowledge. As said in the previous para every information regarding subjects and academic permit is available on social media. It is also remarkable that every latest information regarding current affairs is always available on the social media and in the same way the latest research information for almost every subject of pure science and social science is available for the curious people. This quality of the role and significant source for the promotion of education and the entire academia upto higher and highest level of research and education.

Besides providing current and classified knowledge access to the research scholars the social media also provide means of education counseling to the people concerned.

On the other hand social media has provided access to the international institutions and academic concerns who provide scholarships to the deserving students with respect to merit and also merit cum poverty basis.

2) NEGATIVE ASPECT:

The negative side of the impact of social media with reference to its use for ultra motives of both self and the Mafia and its associates also cannot be ignored. Social media is also being used to promote some unwanted and some ill habits among the people particularly the youth for example use of tobacco and related materials through smoking is being promoted through media.

Use of drugs is also heavily promoted through social media. Those Mafia persons who have expertise in using media propagate the so called “goods” in the use of drugs and deny the

bad. The discussion is a lengthy one but in short the merits of social media are so great in number and quality that the entire humanity seems indebted. In fact through social media "The world is in your hand with just one click".

METHODOLOGY:

The analysis of impact of social media in this paper is based on general view of the social and sale of devices use of media.

Majority of literate people both in urban and rural areas of Sindh are using social media that is its networking sites like facebook, twitter, MSN, google talk, you tube. A large number of people also use modern inventions of social media devices for face to face communication (sort of meeting). Instagram and IMO are also used.

Research studies made by Mr. Hassan "Land Use and Land value in Urban areas" and other scholars of all age groups in the urban areas of the province of Sindh. Particularly in Karachi percentage of usage is the highest upto 90% people use social media daily with different duration of one hour to 3 hours. This usage in general public is mostly for recreation but the students and people related to academic pursuits and to the civic society use social media mostly for academic purpose and for sharing information and also sharing social political comments.

According to studies above 70 percent of the students in Karachi use the social media for academic purpose particularly the internet facility. More than 40% of the users of social media use facebook 32% google talk, 18% snap chats while only 08% use twitter.

The information available at the google says that there is a 5-7 percent growth per annum in the use of social media. A similar figure in growth of sale of IT devices has been recorded all over the country while in Karachi growth rate of users of social media and growth in sale of devices in much more than these figures.

More than 35 million out of 220 million population use media devices while 58% of the users use social media and 18.8% of the users are active members of the social media. These figures in addition to the 5.7 percent growth rate of users of social media and 6.5% growth in the buyers of IT devices used for social media show that entire literature population is using social media and hence its impact is immense.

The analysis of its (social media positive and negative impacts on society is based on the information provided by news items published in newspapers and broadcast on TV channels.

The information collected through news channels and the newspapers show that negative impact is caused by and created by use of blue literature and blue films easily approachable through social media devices.

But it is worthy to be noted that the positive aspect of the impact of social media on society is much appreciable. Academia and media call the internet facility is a stream of information, which help build a news story providing extra but necessary information with latest phase, on the other hand it is equally helpful to the teachers and the taught.

One difficulty or handicap although persists that classified information has been mixed with non classified information but the problems may be overcome by cross checking with the help of internet itself.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSION:

1)The emergence of social media is a blessing in general and may be disguise in a limited preview. It is basis as it is like a river of information flowing with the helm of internet. People of every age group and with any intellectual status could benefit. The disguise is limited as a very small number of people use the devices for observing pornography.

RESOURCE:

Graphs have been taken from research paper of ATM Shahajaha and Kutub Uddin Chishty.

DIFFERENT COMMUNICATIONS COMMUNICATION MEDIA CHOICE MEDIA USING SCHEDULE

TYPES OF COMMUNICATION MEDIA LIKE MOST

1. Social media has established awareness among the people as the comments and free expression regarding social happenings and social events in the society give more knowledge or a knowledge beyond the discourse of the media.
2. Social media has paved a way to turn the world into a global village.
3. Social media help provide correct information and eradicate misinformation.
4. Social media provide the users a chance to ponder upon the sociopolitical situation off the country and also a way to think for its solution.
5. Social media is providing the country folk an awareness regarding local, national and also the international social and political issues together with unlimited information regarding the events related to the walks of life.
6. The impact of social media on our society in totality is positive while the minimized negative aspects of the impact could be done away with the help of the media itself.

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